

Design and Evaluation of Automated Image Quality Screening for Cambodian Identity Documents in Digital Onboarding Systems

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Abstract—This study designed and evaluated a field-based image quality assessment model for Cambodian identity documents used in digital onboarding. The model screens document images before downstream processing by determining whether required identity fields are visually readable. It supports three Cambodian document types: National ID, Driver License, and Passport. The proposed pipeline combines YOLOv11 document localization, YOLOv11 oriented bounding box field detection, fallback cropping, Rule-Based IQA, BRISQUE IQA, and a ResNet-18 CNN-IQA field-readability classifier. The study compares the three IQA pipelines using field-level and document-level metrics, including decision coverage, accuracy excluding Unsure, strict accuracy, macro-F1, field accuracy, mAP50, and mAP50-95. Results show that CNN-IQA achieved the strongest document-level performance, with 96.30% decision coverage, 84.62% accuracy excluding Unsure, 81.48% strict accuracy, and 84.44% macro-F1 across 216 held-out document-level images. At field level, CNN-IQA achieved 89.20% accuracy and 86.77% macro-F1 across 2,112 field crops. The findings indicate that field-based CNN-IQA is more reliable than general whole-image quality assessment for identity document screening because the usability of a submission depends on whether important fields such as name, ID number, date, face photo, and MRZ are readable.

Index Terms—image quality assessment, digital onboarding, e-KYC, Cambodian identity documents, YOLOv11, BRISQUE, CNN-IQA, ResNet-18, field readability

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital onboarding systems increasingly depend on identity document images submitted through mobile devices. In this workflow, the quality of a submitted document image affects downstream tasks such as optical character recognition, document verification, and manual review. A document image may be rejected because of blur, glare, poor lighting, incomplete framing, low contrast, or unreadable identity fields. These issues are especially important in electronic Know Your Customer (e-KYC) workflows, where rejected images slow onboarding while wrongly accepted unreadable images reduce verification reliability.

Cambodian identity documents present practical screening challenges because National IDs, Driver Licenses, and Passports use different layouts, field positions, text sizes, materials, and machine-readable zones. A whole-document image can

appear acceptable while a required field remains unreadable due to localized glare or blur. Therefore, image quality screening should not only estimate general image quality; it should determine whether the required information fields are readable enough for downstream processing.

This study proposes and evaluates an automated image quality screening model for Cambodian identity documents. The work makes three contributions. First, it defines a field-based pipeline that localizes the document, localizes important fields, applies fallback cropping when necessary, and evaluates quality using multiple IQA approaches. Second, it compares Rule-Based IQA, BRISQUE IQA, and CNN-IQA under the same document screening task. Third, it identifies dataset characteristics required for representative Cambodian identity document screening, including multiple document types, realistic mobile capture variation, field-level annotations, field-readability labels, and difficult borderline cases.

II. RELATED WORK

Identity document image screening combines ideas from object detection, no-reference image quality assessment, and supervised image classification. YOLO-based detectors have been widely used for real-time object localization because they provide fast region detection suitable for preprocessing pipelines [1], [4]. In this study, YOLOv11 is used to localize the full document region and YOLOv11 oriented bounding boxes are used to localize fields such as name, ID number, date fields, face photo, and MRZ.

Rule-based image quality assessment is interpretable because it directly measures factors such as blur, brightness, contrast, glare, and visibility. Blur can be estimated using image gradients or Laplacian variance, a common approach in image preprocessing and OCR-quality prediction [2], [6]. However, fixed thresholds can be too strict or too lenient across document types and capture conditions.

BRISQUE is a no-reference image quality assessment method that estimates image naturalness without requiring a clean reference image [7], [8]. It is useful for general quality scoring, but it may not fully represent document-specific readability because a crop may receive an acceptable

TABLE I
DATASET COVERAGE BY DOCUMENT TYPE

Document Type	Images	Participants
National ID	110	22
Driver License	73	14
Passport	71	12

image-quality score even when small text inside the field is unreadable.

CNN-based image quality assessment uses supervised learning to classify image crops based on visual quality or readability [5]. For this project, a ResNet-18 CNN-IQA classifier is trained to classify cropped identity fields as readable or unreadable. This directly matches the screening requirement because identity onboarding depends on whether required fields are usable.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Dataset and Data Handling

The dataset consists of Cambodian identity document images collected under realistic phone-capture conditions. It includes National ID, Driver License, and Passport images. The images were captured using standard consumer smartphones under natural daylight, artificial indoor lighting, and low-light environments. Capture variation included blur, glare, shadow, overexposure, rotation, angled capture, incomplete framing, and background variation.

Because identity documents contain sensitive personal information, data collection followed privacy-controlled handling. Participants provided consent for academic use, and the images were kept in a local research environment. Images were not shared with third-party services, public cloud platforms, or external APIs during testing.

Each image was prepared for document-level and field-level evaluation. Document-level annotation marked the full document region, while field-level annotation marked important information fields such as document number, full name, date of birth, issue date, expiry date, address, face photo, and MRZ where applicable. Images also received q1–q4 quality labels, where q1 represents high-quality readable images, q2 represents usable images with minor quality issues, q3 represents borderline or low-quality images, and q4 represents rejected images.

B. Proposed Screening Pipeline

The proposed model follows a multi-stage pipeline:

- 1) **Document localization:** a YOLOv11 document detector identifies and crops the document region from the input image.
- 2) **Field localization:** document-specific YOLOv11 oriented bounding box detectors localize important fields for each document type.
- 3) **Fallback cropping:** if the field detector misses a required field, a template-based fallback attempts to crop the expected field region.

TABLE II
OVERALL ACCEPTED/REJECTED CLASSIFICATION PERFORMANCE

Metric	Rule	BRISQUE	CNN	Vote
Images	216	216	216	216
Coverage	73.15%	60.65%	96.30%	91.20%
Acc. excl. Unsure	62.66%	61.07%	84.62%	74.62%
Strict accuracy	45.83%	37.04%	81.48%	68.06%
Macro-F1	54.47%	48.86%	84.44%	74.43%

4) **Image quality assessment:** the localized document or field crops are assessed using Rule-Based IQA, BRISQUE IQA, and CNN-IQA.

5) **Decision assignment:** the pipeline outputs Accepted, Unsure, or Rejected depending on the assessed readability and confidence.

C. IQA Pipelines

Rule-Based IQA uses hand-crafted image measurements such as blur, brightness, contrast, glare, and visibility. This approach is fast and interpretable, but depends on manually selected thresholds.

BRISQUE IQA produces no-reference image quality scores for document or field crops. It does not require a clean reference image, making it suitable as a baseline for general quality estimation.

CNN-IQA uses a ResNet-18 field-readability classifier. Instead of only measuring whole-image quality, it classifies whether localized field crops are readable or unreadable. The input to CNN-IQA consists of the field crop and its field type. Its output is used to decide whether the document contains readable required information.

D. Evaluation Metrics

The study uses both localization and classification metrics. Localization was evaluated using mAP50 and mAP50-95. Field-readability classification was evaluated using accuracy and macro-F1. Document-level classification was evaluated using decision coverage, accuracy excluding Unsure, strict accuracy, and macro-F1. Accuracy excluding Unsure measures performance only on images where the method produces a final Accepted or Rejected decision. Strict accuracy counts Unsure as incorrect, making it a more conservative operational metric.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Document-Level Screening Results

The main document-level evaluation used 216 held-out q1–q4 images across Driver License, National ID, and Passport folds. The evaluation includes 73 Driver License images, 106 National ID images, and 37 Passport images.

CNN-IQA produced the strongest overall result. It achieved 84.62% accuracy when Unsure results were excluded and 81.48% strict accuracy when Unsure was counted as incorrect. It also had the highest coverage at 96.30%, meaning it produced a final Accepted or Rejected decision for most

TABLE III
ACCEPTED/REJECTED CLASSIFICATION BY DOCUMENT TYPE

Doc.	Pipeline	Cov.	Acc.	Strict	F1
DL	Rule	65.75	60.42	39.73	48.62
DL	BRISQUE	80.82	71.19	57.53	56.86
DL	CNN	95.89	82.86	79.45	80.98
NID	Rule	78.30	63.86	50.00	58.83
NID	BRISQUE	60.38	50.00	30.19	41.82
NID	CNN	96.23	88.24	84.91	88.24
PP	Rule	72.97	62.96	45.95	46.43
PP	BRISQUE	21.62	75.00	16.22	42.86
PP	CNN	97.30	77.78	75.68	77.78

TABLE IV
FIELD-LEVEL CNN-IQA RESULTS

Document Type	Accuracy	Macro-F1
National ID	89.55%	87.99%
Driver License	89.57%	84.28%
Passport	87.65%	86.10%
Overall	89.20%	86.77%

held-out images. Rule-Based IQA was too conservative, while BRISQUE tended to accept many low-quality images because general image quality did not always reflect field readability. Majority voting did not outperform CNN-IQA because weaker Rule-Based and BRISQUE decisions reduced the benefit of combining pipelines.

National ID produced the strongest document-level result, followed by Driver License and Passport. Passport was the most difficult document type at document level, consistent with weaker MRZ readability and fewer participant samples.

B. Field-Level CNN-IQA Results

Field-level results show whether the CNN-IQA model can classify localized fields as readable or unreadable. Across 2,112 field crops, the CNN-IQA model achieved 89.20% overall accuracy and 86.77% macro-F1.

These results support the use of field-level readability labels. The model performed consistently across the three document types, but difficult fields still need more examples. In the thesis evaluation, Driver License face photo, National ID sex/gender, and Passport MRZ were identified as weaker or more sensitive fields. This indicates that small fields, dense text fields, glossy surfaces, and photo regions require more targeted samples.

C. Dataset Characteristics

The third research question asks what characteristics are required to build a complete representative dataset for Cambodian identity document screening. The results show that clean document images are not enough. A representative dataset must include multiple document types, q1–q4 quality levels, realistic mobile capture conditions, field-level annotations, field-readability labels, difficult borderline cases, balanced participant coverage, and privacy-controlled handling.

Borderline q2/q3 images are especially important because they reveal the weakness of whole-image quality assessment.

A document may appear usable overall while a required field is unreadable due to localized blur, glare, shadow, or low contrast. Therefore, future dataset expansion should focus on difficult field-level examples rather than only increasing the number of clean images.

V. LIMITATIONS

The current study is sufficient for thesis-level evaluation but not production-level generalization. The dataset is limited in size and balance, with Passport having fewer participants than National ID. Field-level labels require manual checking, and borderline q2/q3 cases can be difficult to label consistently. The evaluation also depends on accurate document and field localization before IQA is applied. If localization fails, even a strong readability classifier may receive the wrong crop.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study designed and evaluated an automated image quality screening model for Cambodian identity documents in digital onboarding systems. The results show that YOLO-based localization is useful for standardizing document and field crops, but localization alone should not be the only basis for accepting or rejecting a document. Rule-Based IQA is interpretable and fast, but limited by fixed thresholds. BRISQUE provides a useful no-reference baseline, but is less tailored to document-specific readability. CNN-IQA is the strongest approach in the current evaluation because it directly classifies the readability of important fields rather than relying only on whole-image quality.

The defensible conclusion is that CNN-IQA is the best-performing evaluated pipeline, achieving 96.30% document-level decision coverage, 84.62% accuracy excluding Unsure, 81.48% strict accuracy, and 84.44% macro-F1 across held-out document-level images. At field level, it achieved 89.20% accuracy and 86.77% macro-F1 across 2,112 field crops. Future work should expand participant and document coverage, especially for Passport, MRZ, sex/gender, face photo, and borderline q2/q3 cases; improve localization reliability; and evaluate integration with downstream OCR and e-KYC workflows.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors thank the participants who contributed identity document images for localized academic research. The authors also acknowledge guidance from project advisors and examiners during the development of the proposed Image Quality Assessment model.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Alfahad, "Real time ID card detection using different YOLO models," IEEE Xplore, 2024.
- [2] R. Bansal, G. Raj, and T. Choudhury, "Blur image detection using Laplacian operator and OpenCV," in *Proc. SYSMART*, 2016.
- [3] G. Bradski, "The OpenCV library," *Dr. Dobb's Journal of Software Tools*, 2000.
- [4] G. Jocher, A. Chaurasia, and J. Qiu, "Ultralytics YOLO," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/ultralytics/ultralytics>
- [5] L. Kang, P. Ye, Y. Li, and D. Doermann, "Convolutional neural networks for no-reference image quality assessment," in *Proc. CVPR*, 2014.

- [6] V. C. Kieu, F. Cloppet, and N. Vincent, "OCR accuracy prediction method based on blur estimation," in *Proc. DAS*, 2016.
- [7] Y. Liu, K. F. Yang, and H. M. Yan, "No-reference image quality assessment method based on visual parameters," 2019.
- [8] A. Mittal, A. K. Moorthy, and A. C. Bovik, "No-reference image quality assessment in the spatial domain," *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 21, no. 12, pp. 4695–4708, 2012.
- [9] A. Paszke, S. Gross, F. Massa, et al., "PyTorch: An imperative style, high-performance deep learning library," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, vol. 32, 2019.
- [10] M. Tkachenko, M. Malyuk, A. Holmanyuk, and N. Liubimov, "Label Studio: Data labeling software," 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/HumanSignal/label-studio>
- [11] G. van Rossum and F. L. Drake, *Python 3 Reference Manual*. CreateSpace, 2009.
- [12] K. Verma, "Efficient e-KYC authentication system: Redefining customer verification in digital banking," in *Proc. ICSC*, 2023.